

PEDAGOGICAL MODEL FOR DEVELOPING SOCIO-CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN FUTURE TEACHERS**Sayyorakhon T.Aldasheva****Doctoral Candidate (PhD Student) at Andijan State University****Orcid ID: 0009-0009-5279-5179****<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17505140>****ARTICLE INFO**Received: 29th October 2025Accepted: 30th October 2025Online: 31st October 2025**KEYWORDS**

pedagogical, theoretical and methodological basis, competence, improvement, technological, model, methodological system, socio-cultural competence, tool, ethnoculture, technological basis

ABSTRACT

The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of socio-cultural competence in future teachers, the technological foundations of the development of socio-cultural competence in future teachers based on the subject of "Ethnoculture", the effectiveness of the development of socio-cultural competence in future teachers. The methodological content of the development of socio-cultural competence in future teachers based on the subject of "Ethnoculture" is also analyzed

Introduction

One of the most important educational and moral factors in the learning process of higher education institutions is the communication between professors and students. If, during the organization and implementation of various forms and methods of activity, this interaction acquires a subjective nature — such as humanism, benevolence, and comfort — the effectiveness and impact of teaching and upbringing in higher education institutions increase significantly. In the process of training future specialists, the activity of the professor-teacher as a carrier of spiritual, social, professional, and general culture becomes predominant.

In non-traditional classes, learners gain experience in public speaking, participating in dialogues, engaging in debates, taking initiative, and making important decisions. Through play-based learning, free exchange of ideas and opportunities for creative self-expression emerge, helping students to reveal their personal qualities and individual characteristics while fostering communicativeness and tolerance.

Literature review and methods

Theoretical and methodological foundations for developing socio-cultural competence in future teachers, technological foundations for developing socio-

cultural competence based on the subject “Ethnoculture,” and issues related to the effectiveness of this process have been studied by V.P. Milrud, A. Masovich, D. Kramer, P. Sorokin, R. Merton, T. Parsons, T. Alekseeva, G. Galutskiy, I.F. Isayev, Y.N. Shiyarov, V. Davidov, B. Lednev, S.K. Annamuratova, N.M. Egamberdiyeva, C.Z. Goncharova, V.L. Kraynik, A.G. Abdunabiyev, B. Abdurakhimov, S.Sh. Alimov, A. Erkayev, F.A. Babashev, E. Umarov, M. Rakhmanova, M. Quronov, X. Tojiboyeva, G.J. Tulenova, and Q. Quranboyev.

Results and discussion

Traditional lesson types (combined, new material learning, review-generalization, and assessment) and their conventional forms such as lectures, seminars, and practical-laboratory classes are now acquiring new meaning. In these, the central focus shifts to joint interaction between teacher and learner as the main methodological approach.

When analyzing socio-cultural relations, lessons aimed at self-awareness and self-expression of future teachers were oriented toward students’ inner world, their personal attitude toward the past and the present, and their own value system and worldview. These lessons were conducted in the following forms:

- prototypes of business meetings organized at various levels and in different areas;
- presentations, press conferences, briefings, interviews, teleconferences, round tables, symposiums, auctions, and similar events.

The external format of such meetings was imitated, resembling their formal attributes, while teachers integrated general cultural content into these activities. The lessons designed for material review, consolidation, and control were conducted in non-traditional ways. It should be emphasized that such lessons aroused great interest among students, increased their activity, and showed significantly higher effectiveness.

The content of socio-cultural competence and the problem of its formation are linked with the new pedagogical paradigm of education, which involves abandoning traditional forms (such as mechanical assimilation of ready-made patterns) and emphasizing the development of human potential.

Through an individual and creative approach to understanding the world of culture, values, theories, and the rules of coexistence with other people and cultures, young people develop the ability to construct their own inner world. In this regard, the ideas of N.V. Bordovskaya and A.A. Rean on the relationship

between education and culture are noteworthy. They examine and apply general cultural competence in practice through the following perspectives:

- within the framework of the culturological paradigm of the pedagogical system;
- through methods and means of developing the culture of educational subjects (the pedagogical and intellectual culture of students);
- by characterizing and predicting the cultural and educational image of a person in a specific historical period and revealing the unique features of their cultural and educational sphere;
- by generalizing, preserving, and revitalizing the cultural and educational traditions of the people, ethnic groups, and the nation.

Discussion And Conclusion

The socio-cultural approach ensures the integration of knowledge by studying the significant interconnections of socio-cultural phenomena and processes through the methods and means of understanding cultural studies. It reinforces the application of socio-cultural knowledge in real-life situations and in professional (pedagogical) activities.

From the standpoint of the new paradigm, the pedagogical task consists in developing and gradually implementing a fundamentally new model of teacher education. Its innovativeness lies in the synthesis and equivalence of two major components: general cultural and professional, as well as the harmonious unity of values and technologies.

The expected outcome of such preparation is a specialist who possesses humanitarian, social, and professional competencies — a cultured and qualified future teacher. The unity of these two foundations enables the individual to successfully master developmental, social, and professional technologies; to achieve self-awareness within systems of social norms and relations; and to assimilate innovations of both socio-humanitarian and professional character.

The continuous convergence of professional and general cultural components in training highly qualified, broad-minded specialists ensures the successful fulfillment of the state's educational objectives. The assimilation of national and world culture, spiritual-moral and cultural-historical values and ideals by the developing personality — as well as the understanding of their role and interrelation with past and present social factors — represents one of the urgent problems of pedagogy. Addressing this issue requires designing a special system for forming national and universal cultural competence, along with the conditions for its effective functioning and development.

A higher education institution should serve not only as a center for training specialists, but also as a broad cultural, educational, and moral space where humanistic and ethical values prevail. In the process of preparing future teachers, and in the higher education system in general, the formation of students' national self-awareness plays a vital role. In solving this task, a conscious, emotional, and value-based attitude toward history and human culture is essential: individuals are educated within this culture and ultimately become its bearers and continuators.

An important factor in improving the quality of educational activities at universities is the organizational and educational process, which is complex in nature and encompasses both curricular and extracurricular spheres. An integrated approach views education as a complex, multifaceted, and multistage process whose effectiveness depends on the expansion of the field of social partnership, the cooperation among educated individuals, teachers, the university community, relevant administrative bodies, as well as public, social, and cultural organizations. Only such interaction makes it possible to form a value-oriented attitude toward the socio-cultural components of the profession and to nurture an active interest in real social processes.

In identifying approaches to the development of a pedagogical system for preparing future teachers for the process of developing socio-cultural competence, we considered the contemporary socio-cultural situation and its influence on education and the individual. In the 21st century, the requirements for an educated person are higher than ever: the aim is to form a personality with deep culture, broad humanistic perspectives, creativity, and a global sense of ethics and responsibility — a person who embodies a new humanism in an integrated and indivisible world.

We include among the main external factors of socio-cultural competence development the system of values and leading ideas of society, the lifestyle within macro- and micro-social environments, and the general culture of society. The internal factors include an individual's life experience, value system, adaptation to a multicultural environment, and processes of socialization. The interaction of internal and external factors manifests itself primarily in the student's consciousness — in their worldview, mentality, beliefs, and attitude toward themselves, their country, their people, and the world at large.

The assimilation of external and internal factors into students' consciousness leads to the gradual development of the "I-concept" and the formation of national identity. It should be noted that in the past, insufficient

attention was paid to internal factors such as students' psychological state, moral, social, and cultural upbringing processes. Naturally, this neglect was reflected in the outcomes of educational and developmental activities.

Conclusion

Future teachers are not required to memorize a certain amount of information; instead, they must learn to conduct independent research, explore problems, and find their own solutions. In this way, students do not simply reproduce ready-made constructs — they create new ones based on their existing knowledge and experiences.

Moreover, by performing tasks and solving problems of varying levels of difficulty, students provide teachers with an opportunity to assess their individual level of development and cognitive progress.

In conclusion, it can be stated that the preparation of future teachers for the process of developing socio-cultural competence can be effectively implemented through the use of productive educational approaches, modeling opportunities that demonstrate concrete outcomes, and the active application of innovative methods and educational technologies.

References:

1. Babushkina, L. E. (2011). Sociocultural competence of pedagogical university students: characteristics and formation technologies. *Siberian Pedagogical Journal*.
2. Bordovskaya, N. V., & Rean, A. A. (2009). *Pedagogy: A Study Guide*. St. Petersburg: Piter.
3. Karpova, L. I. (2005). *Formation of Communicative-Grammatical Competence in a Non-Linguistic University (on the material of the English language)* [Doctoral dissertation, RGE]. Moscow.
4. Muslimov, N. A. (2007). *Theoretical and Methodological Foundations of the Professional Formation of Vocational Education Teachers*. Doctoral Dissertation Abstract. Tashkent.
5. Otamuratov, S. (2008). *Globalization and the Nation (Political-Philosophical Analysis)*. Tashkent: Yangi Asr Avlodi.